

An Analysis and Study of *Plumbago Indica* Linn and its Concerning Issues and Characteristics

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Plants have been the subjects of Man's curiosity and purpose since time immemorial. Higher plants are recognized as unique sources of a great variety of commercially important compounds such as pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, flavours, dyes and fragrances." Many of these commercially valuable products come under the general category of 'secondary metabolite'. Secondary metabolites have an ecochemical function; they often represent as chemical adapters to environmental stress or serve as chemical defense of the plant against microorganisms, insect predators or even other plants. Usually, in plant secondary metabolites are accumulated in smaller quantities than primary metabolites. Alkaloids, phenyl propanoids and terpenoids are the predominant class of compounds found in plants.

(Fig.1 *Plumbago indica* Linn)

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with *Plumbago indica* Linn and its characteristics. It is an evergreen perennial herb or shrub growing up to 1.5 metres tall, branched from the base, with the stems drooping and sometimes rooting. The plant is often grown in the backyard for personal use, it is cultivated for medicinal use in India and is also grown as an ornamental in various parts of the tropics, where it is valued for its white inflorescence. Later on this paper the focus is on the medicinal properties of *Plumbago indica*.

Keywords: Rosea, root, plumbagin, plant etc

1. INTRODUCTION

Plumbago indica belong to the family of plumbaginaceae, is an important medicinal plant, cultivated widely in India. The roots of these plant are generally used for medicinal purposes mainly as diuretic, germicidal, vessicant, and abortifacient. It is also used for anaemia, diarrhea, leprosy and common wart. The bark of the root contains orange yellow pigment named plumbagin, a crystalline substance, belongs to the class of naphthoquinone. Its chemical structure is 5-hydroxy 2-methyl 1,4 naphthoquinone. Apart from *P. rosea*, *P. zeylanica*, *P. europea*, *Drosera* and *Drosophyllum* also contains plumbagin. The most exploited source of plumbagin is, of course, *P. rosea* roots. The roots contain 0.9mg/ g D.Wt. of plumbagin in the roots. These plants grow very slowly and the roots suitable for plumbagin extraction can be obtained only after several years of growth. The productivity of the plant is also rather poor.

2. Review of Literature:

Plumbago indica Linn. (Family: Plumbaginaceae) is a shrubby perennial herb, native to the South Asia and at present it is widely cultivated throughout India and Sri Lanka. The regional names of *P. indica* is called in Sinhala as Ratnetol or Ratnitul, in Tamil as Akkini, in Hindi as Chitra (Jayaweera, 1982). *P. indica* is heavily used in Sri Lankan traditional systems of medicine for the preparation of formulations used to treat a variety of disease conditions. The juice of the leaves and roots mixed with oil is employed as an application for rheumatism paralysis and leprosy (Jayaweera, 1982). The roots are used in dyspepsia, colic, inflammations, cough bronchitis helminthiasis, haemorrhoids, elephantiasis chronic intermittent fever, ring worm, hepatosplenomegaly amenorrhoea, odontalgia, anaemia, skin diseases diarrhoea, piles anascarca and as an abortifacient (Satyavathi et al., 1987).

Medicinal plants are of great importance to the health of individual and communities. The medicinal value of these plants lies in some chemical active substances that produce a definite physiological action on the human body. The most important of these chemically active constituents of plants are flavonoids tannins alkaloids saponins and phenolic compounds (Chandur et al., 2011). Plumbagin (5-hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone) is a therapeutically important natural naphthoquinone, occurs mainly in the roots of *P. indica* (Jayaweera, 1982). Studies on the pharmacological

activities of plumbagin have shown the presence of antitumor (Hazra et al., 2008) antimicrobial (Didry et al., 1994, 1998) anticancer (Kuo et al., 2006) antifertility (Bhargava, 1984) antileishmanial (Chan-Bacab and Pena-Rodriguez, 2001) and antiallergic (Dai et al., 2004) properties. Therefore, *P. indica* has increased market demand in both domestic and international level. The slow growth rate absence of seeds and lack of fruiting stage of the *P. indica* in traditional agricultural methods necessitate the search for an alternative and effective source to meet with enhanced commercial demand (Gangopadhyay et al., 2011). According to Gontier et al. (2002), hydroponic culture technique also can be used to produce medicinal plants in large scale.

Tabata et al. (1976) reported that in *Lithospermum erythrorrhizon* cell cultures, metabolite synthesis occurred in highly specialized cells. Fujita et al. (1981) selected a highly productive cell line of *L. erythrorrhizon* and developed a two-stage culture system. In 1983, Mitsui petrochemical marketed the first commercial plant cell line producing shikonin from *L. erythrorrhizon* cell suspension cultures. The cell line developed at Mitsui can accumulate over 20% of shikonin on a dry weight basis, which is 10 times higher than the field grown plants. At present, there are a number of reports on cell cultures producing concentrations of chemical products that are equal to or greater than those found in the whole plant.

3. *Plumbo Indica* in Medicinal Uses:

Indian leadword or *Plumbo Indica* is a popular traditional medicine in India, and also in parts of Africa and southeast Asia - especially where there is a high Indian population]. A poisonous plant, it is valued mainly for external use to treat skin problems, the root being considered the most active part of the plant. The plant is considered to be abortifacient, alterative, carminative, emmenagogue, rubefacient, stimulant, tomachic and vesicant. High doses are dangerous and may cause death. The principle active compound in the plant is the naphthoquinone plumbagin. Other compounds isolated from the aerial parts include 6-hydroxyplumbagin, plumbaginol (a flavonol), leucodelphinidin and steroids (e.g. β -itosterol, stigmaterol, campesterol). Plumbagin possesses several pharmacological activities i.e. antimicrobial, anticancer, cardiotoxic and antifertility actions. It is also a powerful irritant. In small doses, the compound promotes sweating and stimulates the central nervous system; large doses may cause death from respiratory failure and paralysis. Plumbagin has shown anti-implantation and abortifacient activities. At low doses, plumbagin showed significant tumour inhibitory effects against Ehrlich ascites carcinoma. The ethanol extract of the leaves is active against herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1).

The root is used internally to stimulate the digestion; to purify the blood; to promote menstrual flow and/or to induce abortion. A poultice of the roots is used as a remedy for leprosy, rheumatism, paralysis, tumours, headaches toothache, haemorrhoids and swollen glands. The root-bark is used as a vesicant. To this end, the fresh root is cut into very thin slices, which are tied on the skin. Similarly these slices may also be applied to the forehead against eadache.

The leaves are used as a poultice in the treatment of rheumatism and headache.

4. *Plumbo Indica* and its Management:

Plumbago indica can be mass created utilizing in vitro clonal generation of nodal explants, callus societies, cell suspension societies or root societies. The roots of the plants delivered along these lines have an essentially higher level of plumbagin than control plants.

In India tests on root yield of *Plumbago indica* demonstrated an ideal reaping stage somewhere in the range of 12 and year and a half subsequent to planting in the field. *Plumbago indica* is a short-day plant and needs a drawn out dull period treatment in the mild zone so as to create conservative plants and blooms. Fruitful plant recovery through micropropagation utilizing diverse growth media is drilled.

5. Conclusion:

After knowing about *Plumbago indica* and its characteristics its is much clearer that it is an important plant which is helpful in many area specially in medicinal field. This paper is an important asset in the field of botany to understand about this plant and its properties, management etc.

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